

List of contextual elements that are available for you to use:

(This list is also available in the system that you will use to write the requirements. This PDF was created for your convenience only, for example to keep it open in a second screen.)

Entity	Contextual element	Description	Values
User	<u>User</u>	The user who is using the app.	-
User	<u>Account type</u>	Account type (that the user uses to sign in the app)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAUTH • FACEBOOK • TWITTER • GOOGLE • OTHER
User	<u>Role</u>	Role of the user in the app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin of a group • Suggestion worker • DorfFunk support team • Normal (regular user)
Post	<u>Event start date/time</u>	Exact date and time when the event is scheduled to start. Only available when post type is "Event".	-
Post	<u>Author</u>	The user who is the post author	-
Post	<u>Creation time</u>	Exact date and time when the post was created	-
Post	<u>Day type</u>	Day type when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Post	<u>Date/time of last comment</u>	Exact date and time when the latest comment of a post was created	-
Post	<u>Data/time of last like</u>	Exact date and time when the latest like of a post was given	-
Post	<u>Part of the day</u>	Part of the day when the post was created	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn

Post	<u>Type</u>	Type of the post	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free talk (<i>“Plausch”</i>) • Event • News • Offer • Seeking • Suggestion (when the user creates a suggestion, a suggestion worker of the municipality receives it and can interact with the citizen)
Environment	<u>Date/time</u>	Current date/time	-
Environment	<u>Day type</u>	Current day type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workday • Weekend
Environment	<u>Part of the day</u>	Current part of the day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Morning • Noon • Afternoon • Evening • Dawn
Comment	<u>Content type</u>	Type of the content of the comment. Only available when post type is “Event”.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification • Funny • Gratitude • Greeting • Interest • Lament-feeling • Motivation • Opinion • Positive-reaction • Praise • Question • Reminder • Suggestion